

Structure Guided Generation of Thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* *bd* oxidase Inhibitors†

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1. Experimental Section, Chemistry

All anhydrous solvents, reagent grade solvents for chromatography and starting materials were purchased from either Aldrich Chemical Co. (Milwaukee, WI) or Fisher Scientific (Suwanee, GA) unless otherwise noted. The reactions were monitored by TLC on precoated Merck 60 F254 silica gel plates and visualized using UV light (254 nm). All compounds were analyzed for purity by a Bruker micrOTOF with Agilent 1290 UHPLC or Agilent 6520 Q-TOF with Agilent 1100 nano-HPLC and were characterized by ¹H and ¹³C NMR using a Bruker DPX Avance I NMR Spectrometer (300 MHz) and/or a Bruker Ascend Avance III HD Spectrometer (500 MHz) and/or Bruker Avance III Spectrometer (600 MHz). Chemical shifts are reported in ppm (δ) relative to the residual solvent peak in the corresponding spectra; chloroform δ 7.27 and δ 77.23, methanol δ 3.31 and δ 49.00 and coupling constants (*J*) are reported in hertz (Hz) (where, s = singlet, br s = broad singlet, d = doublet, dd = double doublet, bd = broad doublet, ddd = double doublet of doublet, t = triplet, tt=triple triplet, q = quartet, m = multiplet) and analyzed using MestreNova NMR data processing. ¹⁹F NMR were run without a standard and are uncorrected. Mass spectra values are reported as *m/z*. Melting points were measured on a Buchi B-545 melting point instrument and are uncorrected, measured against benzoic acid 118.8-120.2°C.

General procedure A for the preparation of **7**, **10**, **11**, **13**, **17**, **19**, **22**.

In a sealed vial, 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (100 mg, 0.57 mmol), desired amine (0.57 mmol) and K₂CO₃ (79 mg, 0.57 mmol) were dissolved in DMSO (4 mL). The reaction was heated to 100°C for 12 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated to dryness and the residue was dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ and washed with 5% aqueous acetic acid solution (2x), water and brine. The organic phase was collected, dried over sodium sulfate, filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. Crude material obtained was purified by either silica gel column chromatography with a gradient of CH₂Cl₂ : ethyl acetate : solvent system (0 to 80%) or recrystallized from hot isopropanol or acetonitrile to afford the product.

General procedure B for the preparation of **12**, **14-16**, **18**, **20**, **21**.

In a sealed vial, 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (100 mg, 0.57 mmol, 1 equiv.) and amine (1 equiv.) were dissolved in a 3:1 tetrahydrofuran: 2-propanol solution (4 mL). Next, 12 M HCl (11 μL, “drop”, ~0.4 equiv.) was added. The solution heated to 70°C for 24 h. The reaction was concentrated to dryness and the residue was dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ and washed with saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ solution, water, and brine. The organic phase was collected, dried over sodium sulfate, filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. Crude material obtained was purified by either silica gel column chromatography with a gradient of CH₂Cl₂ : ethyl acetate : solvent system (0-80%) or recrystallized from hot isopropanol or acetonitrile to afford the product.

N-(3-(Trifluoromethyl)phenethyl)thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**7**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure A using 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (50 mg, 0.28 mmol), 2-(3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)ethan-1-amine (55 mg, 0.38 mmol), potassium carbonate (39 mg, 0.28 mmol) to give **7** as a yellow flaky solid (32 mg, 33% yield). m.p. 109.8-111.4°C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm 8.68 (s, 1H), 7.72 (d, *J* = 5.4 Hz, 1H), 7.55-7.51 (m, 2H), 7.47-7.43 (m, 3H), 5.06 (br s, 1H), 3.97 (q, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 2H), 3.11 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm 159.8, 157.2, 155.0, 139.7, 132.3, 130.9, 129.1, 125.5, 123.5, 115.2, 42.2, 35.6. ¹⁹F (282 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm -62.56 (s, 3F). HRMS (EI), *M* + 1 calculated for C₁₅H₁₂F₃N₃S, 324.0777, found 324.0890; HPLC *t*_R = 5.9 min, >95% pure.

N-(2-(Trifluoromethyl)phenethyl)thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**10**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure A using 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (100 mg, 0.57 mmol), 2-(2-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)ethan-1-amine (0.09 mL, 0.57 mmol), potassium carbonate (79 mg, 0.57 mol) to give **10** as white, fluffy crystals (80.8 mg, 42%). m.p. 141.5-141.8°C. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm 8.68 (s, 1H), 7.72 (d, *J* = 5.3 Hz, 1H), 7.68 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 7.51 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 1 H), 7.46-7.42 (m, 2H), 7.36 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 5.13 (s, 1H), 3.96 (q, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 2H), 3.24 (t, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm 159.8, 157.2, 155.1, 137.4, 131.9, 131.7, 130.8, 126.7, 125.5, 123.5, 121.3, 115.2, 42.2, 23.5. ¹⁹F (470 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm -59.2 (s, 3F). HRMS (EI), *M* + 1 calculated for C₁₅H₁₂F₃N₃S, 324.0777, found 324.0786; HPLC *t*_R = 6.4 min, >95% pure.

N-(4-(Trifluoromethyl)phenethyl)thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**11**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure A using 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (100 mg, 0.57 mmol), 2-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)ethan-1-amine (108 mg, 0.57 mmol), and potassium carbonate (79 mg, 0.57 mmol) to give **11** as yellow crystals (75.1 mg, 39%). m.p. 171.0-171.5°C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm 8.68 (s, 1H), 7.72 (d, *J* = 5.4 Hz, 1H), 7.60 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 2H), 7.44 (d, *J* = 5.4 Hz, 1H), 7.38 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 5.08 (s, 1H), 3.97 (q, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 2H), 3.11 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm 159.89, 157.16, 155.03, 142.98, 130.89, 129.23, 125.10 (q, *J* = 15.0 Hz), 125.52, 123.13, 120.97, 115.22, 42.13, 35.60. ¹⁹F (470 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm -62.43 (s, 3F). HRMS (EI), *M* + 1 calculated for C₁₅H₁₂F₃N₃S, 324.0777, found 324.0780; HPLC *t*_R = 6.5 min, >95% pure.

N-Phenethylthieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**12**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure B using 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (100 mg, 0.57 mmol), 2-phenylethan-1-amine (0.07 mL, 0.57 mmol) and 12 N HCl (11 μ L, 0.13 mmol) to give **12** as yellow, sand-like crystals (35.1 mg, 24%). m.p. 173.0-173.5°C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ ppm 8.46 (s, 1H), 8.08 (d, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.94 (t, $J = 5.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.37 (d, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.32-7.24 (m, 4H), 7.20 (t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.72 (q, $J = 6.9$ Hz, 2H), 2.94 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO) δ ppm 159.69, 157.30, 155.04, 139.99, 133.26, 129.15, 128.81, 126.56, 124.91, 115.15, 42.29, 35.34. HRMS (EI), $M + 1$ calculated for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{S}$, 256.0903, found 256.0911; HPLC $t_{\text{R}} = 5.6$ min, >95% pure.

N-(4-(Trifluoromethoxy)phenethyl)thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**13**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure A using 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (100 mg, 0.57 mmol), 2-(4-(trifluoromethoxy)phenyl)ethan-1-amine (120 mg, 0.57 mmol), and potassium carbonate (81 mg, 0.57 mmol) to give **13** as a white solid (39.2 mg, 20%). m.p. 129.0-130.8°C. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO) δ ppm 8.46 (s, 1H), 8.09 (d, $J = 5.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.95 (t, $J = 5.5$ Hz, 1H, NH), 7.40-7.36 (m, 3H), 7.28 (d, $J = 7.9$ Hz, 2H), 3.73 (q, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 2H), 2.98 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, DMSO) δ ppm 159.7, 157.3, 155.0, 147.3, 139.6, 133.3, 130.9, 124.9, 121.4, 119.7, 115.1, 42.0, 34.5. ^{19}F (282 MHz, DMSO) δ ppm -56.8 (s, 3F). HRMS (EI), $M + 1$ calculated for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{F}_3\text{N}_3\text{OS}$, 340.0726, found 340.0741; HPLC $t_{\text{R}} = 5.5$ min, >95% pure.

N-(4-(Trifluoromethoxy)benzyl)thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**14**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure B using 4-chloro-thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (50 mg, 0.29 mmol), 4-(trifluoromethoxy)benzylamine (56 mg, 0.29 mmol), and 12 M HCl (11 μ L, 0.13 mmol). Crude material was purified through column chromatography (ethyl acetate) to give **14** as an orange solid (21.2 mg, 22%). m.p. 109.5-109.9°C. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm 8.60 (s, 1H), 7.67 (d, $J = 5.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.40 (d, $J = 5.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.31 (t, $J = 7.9$ Hz, 1H), 7.26 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 1H), 7.20-7.17 (m, 1H), 7.09 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz, 1H), 5.30 (br.s, 1H), 4.84 (d, $J = 5.9$ Hz, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm 157.1, 154.8, 149.6, 140.6, 131.3, 130.2, 126.0, 125.4, 120.3, 120.0, 115.2, 44.4. ^{19}F (282 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm -57.7 (s, 3F). HRMS (EI), $M + 1$ calculated for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{F}_3\text{N}_3\text{OS}$, 326.0569, found 326.0568; HPLC $t_{\text{R}} = 6.5$ min, >95% pure.

N-(4-(Trifluoromethoxy)phenyl)thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**15**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure B using 4-chloro-thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (60 mg, 0.35 mmol), 4-(trifluoromethoxy)aniline (62 mg, 0.35 mmol), and 12 M HCl (11 μ L, 0.13 mmol) to give **15** as a yellow solid (49.6 mg, 45%). m.p. 151.2-151.8°C. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm 8.77 (s, 1H), 7.79 (d, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.70 (dt, $J = 9.0, 3.3$ Hz, 2H), 7.49 (d, $J = 5.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.31-7.26 (m, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm 161.2, 155.6, 154.6, 146.1, 136.4, 123.4, 125.4, 124.3, 121.8, 115.5. ^{19}F (282 MHz, DMSO) δ ppm -58.0 (s, 3F). HRMS (EI), $M + 1$ calculated for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_8\text{F}_3\text{N}_3\text{OS}$, 312.0413, found 312.0425; HPLC $t_{\text{R}} = 5.8$ min, >95% pure.

N-(4-Methoxyphenethyl)thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**16**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure B using 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (100 mg, 0.57 mmol), 2-(4-methoxyphenyl)ethan-1-amine (0.09 mL, 0.57 mmol), and 12 M HCl (11 μ L, 0.13 mmol) to give **16** as a shiny bronze solid (75.4 mg, 46%). m.p. 151.5-151.7°C. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm 8.67 (s, 1H), 7.71 (d, J = 5.3 Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, J = 5.3 Hz, 1H), 7.18 (dt, J = 8.6, 3.0 Hz, 2H), 6.89 (dt, J = 8.6, 3.0 Hz, 2H), 3.92 (q, J = 6.8 Hz, 2H), 3.83 (s, 3H), 2.98 (t, J = 6.8 Hz, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm 159.7, 158.4, 157.3, 155.0, 130.8, 130.6, 129.8, 125.25, 115.2, 114.2, 55.3, 42.6, 34.8. HRMS (EI), $M + 1$ calculated for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{OS}$, 286.1009, found 286.0998; HPLC t_{R} = 5.6 min, >95% pure.

N-(4-(Pentafluoro- λ^6 -sulfanyl)phenethyl)thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**17**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure A using 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (72 mg, 0.42 mmol), 2-(4-(pentafluoro- λ^6 -sulfanyl)phenyl)ethan-1-amine (105 mg, 0.42 mmol), and potassium carbonate (59 mg, 0.42 mmol) to give **17** as a white solid (59.3 mg, 36%). m.p. 288.1-288.2°C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ ppm 8.46 (s, 1H), 8.09 (d, J = 5.4 Hz, 1H), 7.94 (t, J = 5.4 Hz, 1H), 7.82 (d, J = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 7.48 (d, J = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 7.38 (d, J = 5.4 Hz, 3.76 (q, J = 6.8 Hz, 2H), 3.05 (t, J = 6.8 Hz, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm 159.7, 157.3, 155.0, 145.2, 133.4, 130.2, 126.2, 124.9, 115.2, 41.7, 34.7; ^{19}F NMR (282 MHz, DMSO) δ ppm 84.5 (penta, J = 150.0 Hz, 1F), 63.0 (d, J = 150.0 Hz, 4F); HRMS (EI), $M + 1$ calculated for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{F}_5\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$, 382.0466; found 382.0476; HPLC t_{R} = 6.8 min, >95% pure.

N-(4-Methylphenethyl)thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**18**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure B using 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (100 mg, 0.57 mmol), 2-(*p*-tolyl)ethan-1-amine (79 mg, 0.57 mmol), and 12 M HCl (11 μ L, 0.13 mmol) to give **18** as pale yellow crystals (75.1 mg, 47%). m.p. 186.8-190.0°C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm 8.46 (s, 1H), 8.08 (d, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.91 (t, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.37 (d, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.15 (d, $J = 7.9$ Hz, 2H), 7.90 (d, $J = 7.9$ Hz, 2H), 3.69 (q, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 2H), 2.89 (t, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 2H), 2.27 (s, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm 159.7, 157.3, 155.0, 136.9, 135.5, 133.2, 129.4, 129.0, 124.9, 42.4, 34.9, 21.1. HRMS (EI), $M + 1$ calculated for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{S}$, 270.1059, found 270.1051; HPLC $t_{\text{R}} = 6.1$ min, >95% pure.

N-(4-(*tert*-Butyl)phenethyl)thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**19**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure A using 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (100 mg, 0.57 mmol), 2-(4-(*tert*-butyl)phenyl)ethan-1-amine (106 mg, 0.57 mmol), and potassium carbonate (79 mg, 0.57 mmol) to give **19** as a yellow solid (103 mg, 55%). m.p. 133.8-134.5°C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm 8.66 (s, 1H), 7.70 (d, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.38 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 2H), 7.20 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 2H), 5.03 (s, 1H), 3.95 (q, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 2H), 3.01 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 2H), 1.35 (s, 9H). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm 159.9, 157.3, 155.1, 149.6, 135.6, 130.7, 128.5, 125.6, 125.5, 115.2, 64.41, 42.4, 35.2, 34.5, 31.4. HRMS (EI), $M + 1$ calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{S}$, 312.1534 found, 312.1520; HPLC $t_{\text{R}} = 5.8$ min, >95% pure.

N-(4-Chlorophenethyl)thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**20**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure B using 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (100 mg, 0.57 mmol), 2-(4-chlorophenyl)ethan-1-amine (0.08 mL, 0.57 mmol), and 12 M HCl (11 μ L, 0.13 mmol) to give **20** as a pale yellow, flaky solid (34.7 mg, 20%). m.p. 174.2-175.0°C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm 8.67 (s, 1H), 7.72 (d, J = 5.4 Hz, 1H), 7.45 (d, J = 5.4 Hz, 1H), 7.31 (dt, J = 8.4, 2.6 Hz, 2H), 7.21-7.16 (m, 2H), 5.00 (br.s, 1H), 3.92 (q, J = 6.7 Hz, 2H), 3.02 (t, J = 6.7 Hz, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ ppm 159.7, 157.2, 154.9, 137.2, 132.5, 130.9, 130.2, 128.8, 125.5, 115.2, 42.3, 35.1. HRMS (EI), $M + 1$ calculated for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClN}_3\text{S}$, 290.0513 found, 290.0513; HPLC t_{R} = 6.2 min, >95% pure.

N-(3,4-Dichlorophenethyl)thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**21**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure B using 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (100 mg, 0.57 mmol), 2-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)ethan-1-amine (0.09 mL, 0.57 mmol), and 12 M HCl (11 μ L, 0.13 mmol) to give **21** as a yellow brown pebble-like solid (35.1 mg, 18%). m.p. 186.1-187.2°C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, MeOD) δ ppm 8.45 (s, 1H), 7.97 (d, J = 5.4 Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, J = 1.9 Hz, 1H), 7.41 (d, J = 8.2 Hz, 1H), 7.35 (d, J = 5.4 Hz, 1H), 7.18 (dd, J = 8.2, 1.9 Hz, 1H), 3.83 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.00 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, MeOD) δ ppm 158.2, 157.4, 154.0, 140.2, 132.4, 131.7, 130.7, 130.0, 129.7, 128.6, 123.4, 115.4, 41.5, 34.2. HRMS (EI), $M + 1$ calculated for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_3\text{S}$, 324.0124, found 324.0132; HPLC t_{R} = 6.7 min, >95% pure.

N-(4-(Dimethylamino)phenethyl)thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**22**). The reaction was carried out according to the general procedure A using 4-chlorothieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (100 mg, 0.57 mmol), 4-(2-aminoethyl)-*N,N*-dimethylaniline (0.10 mL, 0.57 mmol), and potassium carbonate (79 mg, 0.57 mmol) to give **22** as pale yellow crystals (88.3 mg, 49%). m.p. 169.5-171.7°C. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm 8.66 (s, 1H), 7.69 (d, *J* = 5.3 Hz, 1H), 7.43 (d, *J* = 5.3 Hz, 1H), 7.14 (d, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 1H), 6.74 (d, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 1H), 5.02 (br.s, 1H), 3.90 (q, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 2H), 2.96 (s, 6H), 2.93 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm 162.26, 159.71, 157.33, 155.06, 149.57, 130.74, 129.51, 125.44, 113.10, 42.67, 40.77, 34.65. HRMS (EI), *M* + 1 calculated for C₁₆H₁₈N₄S 299.1325 found, 299.1320; HPLC *t*_R = 4.2 min, >95% pure.

2. NMR spectra

SMH1-36.10.fid
7 (CDCl₃, 500 MHz)

SMH1-36.12.fid
7 (CDCl₃, 125 MHz)

159.7861
157.1588
154.9610

139.7314

132.3197

130.9490

129.1285

125.4695

123.5671

115.2330

42.1813

35.6295

SMH1-36-19F.1.fid
7 (CDCl₃, 282 MHz)

-62.5618

SMH1-31-13307-proton.10.f1
10 (CDCl3, 600 MHz)

SMH1-31-13307-carbon-10.fid
10 (CDCl₃, 150 MHz)

159.2366
157.1761
155.0834
137.3934
131.9357
131.7152
130.8159
126.7241
125.4766
123.6755
115.2490

SMH1-31.12.fid
10 (CDCl₃, 470 MHz)

—59.2431

SMH1-32.10.fid
11 (CDCl3, 500 MHz)

SMH1-32.12.fid
11 (CDCl₃, 125 MHz)

159.8936
157.1605
155.0335
142.9585
130.8921
129.2260
125.6475
125.6175
125.5875
125.5577
125.5212
123.1288
120.9670
115.2206

42.1316
35.6032

SMH1-32.11.fid
11 (CDCl₃, 470 MHz)

SMH1-6.10.fid
12 (DMSO, 500 MHz)

8.4616
8.0855
8.0748
7.9535
7.9429
7.9322
7.3757
7.3650
7.2147
7.2006
7.1866

3.7426
3.7294
3.7137
3.7015

2.9552
2.9399
2.9252

SMH1-6.11.fid
12 (DMSO, 125 MHz)

— 159.6909
— 157.3039
— 155.0449

— 139.9909

— 133.2574

— 129.1482

— 128.8085

— 126.5579

— 124.9054

— 115.1474

— 42.2888

— 35.3380

GM34-60-1-11978-proton.10.fig
13 (DMSO, 600 MHz)

GM34-60-1-11978-carbon-130.fid
13 (DMSO, 150 MHz)

GM34-60-1-11978-19F.1.fid
13 (DMSO, 282 MHz)

-56.8069

GM44-41-3-13541-protos.10.fid
14 (CDCl3, 600 MHz)

8.5969
7.6741
7.6652
7.4015
7.3926
7.3261
7.3130
7.2999
7.2690
7.2561
7.0969
7.0834

GM44-41-3-19541-carbon.10.f1
14 (CDCl3, 150 MHz)

GM44-41-3-13541-19F.1.fid
14 (CDCl₃, 282 MHz)

—57.6964

GM44-36-1-13312-proton.10.fid
15 (CDCl3, 600 MHz)

GM44-36-1-13312-carbon-13
15 (CDCl₃, 150 MHz)

161.1591
161.1599
155.6122
154.6262
146.1395
136.3713
132.3765
125.3524
124.2801
121.7859
119.6483
115.5010

GM44-36-1-13312-19F.1.fid
15 (CDCl₃, 282 MHz)

-58.0123

SMH1-8-13297-proton.10.fid
16 (CDCl3, 600 MHz)

8.666
7.7131
7.7042
7.4493
7.4404
7.1945
7.1896
7.1864
7.1785
7.1753
7.1705
6.9064
6.8981
6.8905
6.8871
6.8822

4.9722

3.9325
3.9210
3.9111
3.8996
3.8270

2.9886
2.9771
2.9655

SMH1-8-13297-carbon
16 (CDCl₃, 150 MHz)

159.7444
158.4277
157.2778
155.0428

130.7856
130.6106
129.8265
125.4707

115.1807
114.1753

55.3053

42.5790

34.8049

GM34-86-1-12066.10.tif
17 (DMSO, 500 MHz)

8.4647
8.0922
8.0815
7.9527
7.9419
7.9310
7.8242
7.8068
7.4918
7.4751
7.3823
7.3716

3.7824
3.7688
3.7565
3.7428

3.0595
3.0452
3.0310

GM34-86-1-12066.11.6
17 (DMSO, 125 MHz)

GM34-86-1-SF5.1.fid
17 (DMSO, 282 MHz)

smh-2-13-1-13304.10.fid
18 (DMSO, 500 MHz)

8.4609
8.0849
8.0742
7.9206
7.9099
7.8991
7.3751
7.3644
7.1530
7.1371
7.1094
7.0936

3.7143
3.7018
3.6876
3.6851
3.6731
2.9075
2.8922
2.8775

2.2657

0.87

0.95

0.97

0.95

1.99

2.07

2.04

2.03

3.00

10.0 9.5 9.0 8.5 8.0 7.5 7.0 6.5 6.0 5.5 5.0 4.5 4.0 3.5 3.0 2.5 2.0 1.5 1.0 0.5 0.0

f1 (ppm)

110000
100000
90000
80000
70000
60000
50000
40000
30000
20000
10000
0
-10000

smh-2-13-143884.11.fid
18 (DMSO, 125 MHz)

smh1-33-10137.10.fid
19 (CDCl3, 500 MHz)

smh1-33-10137.11.ft
19 (CDCl3, 125 MHz)

159.8631
157.3146
155.1120
149.5816
135.5788
130.7312
128.5419
125.6376
125.4896
115.1895

42.4070
35.1899
34.4561
31.3777

SMH1-17.10.fid
20 (CDCl3, 500 MHz)

SMH1-17.1251
20 (CDCl₃, 125.76 MHz)

smh-2-12-1-13298.10.fid
21 (MeOD, 500 MHz)

smh-2-12-1-1328811.fid
21 (MeOD, 125.761 Hz)

SMH2-18-1-13311.12.fid
22 (CDCl3, 600 MHz)

SMH2-18-1-13311.13
22 (CDCl₃, 150 MHz)

159.4093
157.3216
155.1362

130.6864
129.5044
126.3784
125.4643

113.0791

42.6586
40.7634

34.6451

3. Experimental section, Biology

Screening assay

Mycobacterium bovis BCG and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains were cultured in Middlebrook 7H9 medium (Becton Dickson and Company Limited, USA) supplemented with 0.05% tween 80, 0.5% glycerol, Bovine Serum Albumin Fraction V, D-glucose, and NaCl. *M. tuberculosis* clinical isolate N0145 was a gift from Sebastien Gagneux. Prior to use, bacteria cells were pelleted and resuspended in medium without glycerol and adjusted to an approximated cell density of 10^7 CFU/mL. 1 μ L of test compounds of varying concentrations were added to each well of 96-well white plates, and 100 μ L of bacterial culture was subsequently added to each well. The assay plates were incubated at 37°C for 15 hours, after which the BacTiter-Glo™ (Promega, USA) reagent was added. Following a 12-minute delay, the luminescence of each plate was measured using a BioTek Cytation 3 Cell Imaging Multiple-mode reader. IC₅₀ values were determined using GraphPad Prism 8.4.